

Shannon's Entropy and Two Coupled Oscillators

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In previous notes (1) we discussed the free particle classical action in the form $A = -Et + px$ in which p, x and E and t are independent for the relative and nonrelativistic cases. This leads to a scenario in which one cannot follow a particle in time i.e. there does not exist an $x(t)$ as in classical mechanics. Instead one may develop eigenvalue equations $-i \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $i \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ for the free particle. The solution $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ is similar to a classical wave (which is a different solution following form $A = -Et + px$) in that it describes a kind of probability resonance in all of space. If one introduces a potential $V(x)$, this is localized and one needs to think in terms of impulse hit resonances like $\exp(ikx)$ creating $V(x)$. In other words, both an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$ representing the particle and $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ are described in terms of this resonance type periodic probability which interferes to create local features. One might argue that this feature of $V(x)$ drives the particle.

In this note we wish to examine the coupled oscillator $H = p_1^2/2m + p_2^2/2m + \frac{1}{2}k_1 x_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}k_2 x_2^2 + \frac{1}{2}k_3 (x_1 - x_2)^2$ (with $m=1$). Transforming variables leads to an equation with a separable solution, but in $y = x_1 + x_2$ and $y_1 = x_1 - x_2$. In this note we try to examine this solution in terms of the above resonance picture and also suggest a possible overall Shannon's entropy.

Free Particle Classical Action

The relativistic $(-m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})$ and nonrelativistic $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ classical actions A may be written in terms of $v = x/t$ and these two variable varied independently to yield (1):

$$\frac{dA}{dx} \text{partial} = p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dA}{dt} \text{partial} = -E \quad ((1b))$$

Treating x and t as independent means one rejects $x(t)$ which is a fundamental idea of classical mechanics. In other words, the particle has properties p and E linked to any x or time t . It is almost as if one has resonance throughout x and t . An overall solution of A is $-Et + px$. This may be linked to eigenvalue equations:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad i \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((2b))$$

$\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ then describes a kind of wavelike probability resonance which exists in space and time with x and t being independent. For a single particle bound state, one may create an ensemble of $\exp(-iE_n t + ipx)$ terms where E_n is a constant bound state energy. Assuming an average constant energy at each point x because one uses $V(x)$ and such conservation exists in the classical picture then:

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{2m} \sum_p a(p) p^2 \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where} \quad W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$$

This is equivalent to the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

One may also consider $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ as a series of resonance impulse momentum hits. Thus one gives up the local $x(t)$ and $V(x)$ with acceleration scenario and considers free particle periodic resonances throughout space $\exp(-iE_n t + ipx)$ combining with impulse hit resonance $V_k \exp(ikx)$ from $V(x)$ to create an overall resonance linked to $W_n(x)$ the wavefunction and E_n . For a single particle, k represents the momentum of a particle if it were to be ejected from the system, but it also represents the momentum of a space invariant probability resonance which interferes with other probability resonances to create the overall $W_n(x)$.

Coupled Two Oscillator

The above approach may be applied to a particle oscillator for which there are two walls with a particle of $m=1$ attached to a spring with $k=w_1 w_1$ at each wall. The two particles are joined in the middle by a spring with $k_2=w_2 w_2$. The Hamiltonian (2) is:

$$H = p_1^2/2 + p_2^2/2 + .5w_1 w_1 (x_1^2 + x_2^2) + .5w_2 w_2 (x_1 - x_2)^2 \quad ((4))$$

Changing variable to $y = (x_1 + x_2)$ and $y_1 = (x_1 - x_2)$ and using $p_a = -i d/dy$, $p_b = -i d/dy_1$ yields:

$$H = -.5 d/dy d/dy + .5(w_+)(w_+)yy - .5 d/dy_1 d/dy_1 + .5(w_-)(w_-)y_1 y_1 \quad ((5))$$

where $(w_+)(w_+) = .5w_1 w_1$ and $(w_-)(w_-) = .5w_1 w_1 + w_2 w_2$

One obtains two decoupled oscillator Hamiltonians, but in unusual variables y and y_1 . For a classical mechanical picture this is somewhat problematic as one follows $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$. It is then surprising to have $(x_1(t) - x_2(t))$ and $(x_1(t) + x_2(t))$ as physical entities. In quantum mechanics free particle probabilities for y and y_1 are:

$$\exp(ikx_1) \exp(ikx_2) \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(ipx_1) \exp(-ipx_2) \quad ((6))$$

One does not follow the particles in space through $x(t)$, but rather has resonance $\exp(ipx)$ for each particle. ((6)) seems to suggest that the particles have correlated momenta and that there are two sets of correlated momenta resonances. These are consistent with the resonances associated with the two potential terms in ((5)) driving the overall final resonance solution of the two coupled oscillators. In other words the mathematical decoupling of ((4)) seems to have a physical interpretation in the quantum picture which is based on free particle resonances, but now with correlations. It may be noted that the weights of the two pieces in ((6)) $a(k)$ and ((7)) $b(p)$ represent two sets of correlated momenta, not the momenta of particle 1 and particle 2. Rather one deals with two resonances which interfere to create an overall new final solution resonance. The interesting feature is that within each resonance one has correlated momenta of the x_1 and x_2 .

A solution of ((5)) is $W_n(y)W_j(y_1)$ ((7)) where W_n and W_k are solutions of a single oscillator equation i.e. $\exp(-axx)$ multiplied by a Hermite polynomial. In general one may create linear combinations of various ((7)) or consider a pure state such as the ground state i.e. $W_0(y)W_0(j)$

Shannon's Entropy for the Two Coupled Oscillators

In (2) a calculation is performed for the reduced von Neumann density of a coupled oscillator $W_0(y)W_0(y_1)$ pure state. The overall density in such a case is:

$$W_0(y')W_0(y_1')W_0(y)W_0(y_1) = W_0(x'a+x'b)W_0(x'a-x'b) W_0(xa+xb)W_0(xa-xb) \quad ((8))$$

The reduced density is obtained by setting $x_b=x'b$ and integrating over x_b . The final result has the appearance of a von Neumann density of a single oscillator (with a certain w and T temperature given in terms of w^+ and w^-). This is then linked to the entropy of a single oscillator i.e. $-\sum_n \exp(-E_n/T)/C(T) [(-E_n/T) - \ln(C(T))]$. ((9))

For a single particle pure bound state one may calculate a Shannon's entropy. In the literature (3), two Shannon entropies i.e. S_p and S_x are usually calculated and kept separate. We have suggested in previous notes using

$$P(x)P(p/x) = a(p)W(x)\exp(-ipx) \quad ((10))$$

as the probability in Shannon's entropy equation $-\sum_i P(i)\ln(P(i))$. This yields

$$S = .5S_p + .5S_x \text{ i.e. a sum.}$$

For the case of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, L the size of the box disappears from S so one may perform a quantum adiabatic transformation which would also be isentropic. The same result holds if one has a single particle oscillator and changes the spring constant quantum adiabatically. We wish to point out that x and p in this case represent a single particle, X is associated with any x point. P on the other hand is a specific constant, but the $a(p)$'s in $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ range over all all p values.

$$\text{If one postulates: Probability} = a_n(p) \exp(-ipy) a_j(k) \exp(-iky_1) W_n(y)W_j(y_1) \quad ((10))$$

where W_n is an oscillator eigenfunction i.e. $\exp(-axx)$ Hermite polynomial(n) (x) then:

$$\text{Shannon's entropy} = -\sum_p a_n(p) a_n(p) \ln(a_n(p)) - \sum_k a_j(k) a_j(k) \ln(a_j(k))$$

$$+ -\sum_y W_n(y) W_n(y) \ln(W_n(y)) - \sum_{y_1} W_j(y_1) W_j(y_1) \ln(W_j(y_1))$$

$$+ \sum_{k, y_1} iky_1 a_j(k) \exp(-iky_1) W_j(y_1) + \sum_{p, y} ipy a_n(p) \exp(-ipy) W_n(y)$$

The last two terms integrate to 2 a constant which may be dropped i.e.

$W=W^*$ for a bound state so:

$\int \frac{d}{dy} (y W W) = 0 = \int W W dy + 2 \int y W \frac{dW}{dy}$ where $\int W W dy=1$

Shannon's entropy = - Sum over p $a_n(p) a_n(p) \ln(a_n(p))$ - Sum over k $a_j(k) a_j(k) \ln(a_j(k))$

- Sum over y $W_n(y) W_n(y) \ln(W_n(y))$ - Sum over y1 $W_j(y1) W_j(y1) \ln(W_j(y1))$ ((11))

This has the appearance of a sum of two oscillator entropies, but p and k are not the momenta of the two particles and y and y1 mix both variables x1 and x2. Rather one seems to have the sum of entropies of two resonance disturbances, one described by $W_n(y)$ and the other by $W_j(y1)$. The two resonance disturbances create an overall final solution resonance which is the two particle coupled oscillator solution. Thus in quantum mechanics Shannon's entropy seems to be linked to the entropy of a resonance not of particle motion.

We also note that if one changes w1 and w2 quantum adiabatically, the form of entropy ((11)) leads to the elimination of the spring constants and so the coupled system would also change isentropically.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that the classical action approach (1) of a single free quantum particle which is to reject the idea of $x(t)$ and consider a probability resonance in all of space of $\exp(ipx)$ as representing the particle leads to an interesting interpretation of the two particle coupled oscillator problem. The Hamiltonian is not separable in $x1$ and $x2$, but is separable in $y=x1+x2$ and $y1=x1-x2$. Thus one may mathematically solve the problem in quantum mechanics and obtain $W_n(y) W_j(y1)$ (or linear combinations). The question is: What is the interpretation? We argue that instead of following the motion of the two particles $x1(t)$ and $x2(t)$ one considers two resonances which are stirred up by the potential. Both particles are part of both resonances, but have different momentum correlations in each. In the first resonance, the two particles have the same momentum i.e. $\exp(ipx1) \exp(ipx2)$. One takes linear combinations of $\exp(i p(x1+x2))$ changing p values. In the other resonance one has the correlation $\exp(ikx1) \exp(-ikx2)$ i.e one particle has k and the other -k leading to $\exp(ik(x1-x2))$. It is no longer the particle identity which matters, but the identities of the two resonances which add to create the overall final solution resonance. When calculating Shannon's entropy for the overall system we argue that the result is the sum of Shannon's entropy of each resonance. Thus each two particle correlated momentum resonance each behave as a kind of separate system with the sum giving the overall entropy (like in classical thermodynamics).

References

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